

High-Throughput and Combinatorial Approaches for the Development of Multifunctional Polymers

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High-throughput (HT) development of new multifunctional polymers is accomplished by the combination of different HT tools established in polymer sciences in the last decade. Important advances are robotic/HT synthesis of polymer libraries, the HT characterization of polymers, and the application of spatially resolved polymer library formats, explicitly microarray and gradient libraries. HT polymer synthesis enables the generation of material libraries with combinatorial design motifs. Polymer composition, molecular weight, macromolecular architecture, etc. may be varied in a systematic, fine-graded manner to obtain libraries with high chemical diversity and sufficient compositional resolution as model systems for the screening of these materials for the functions aimed. HT characterization allows a fast assessment of complementary properties, which are employed to decipher quantitative structure–properties relationships. Moreover, these methods facilitate the HT determination of important surface parameters by spatially resolved characterization methods, including time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Here current methods for the high-throughput robotic synthesis of multifunctional polymers as well as their characterization are presented and advantages as well as present limitations are discussed.

design, which is the stepwise adaption of known materials and their properties in a serial manner to converge on the desired material characteristics. This tedious approach might lead to success, however, to be competitive in industry or academia it is necessary to accelerate this process and adapt the research speed to the shortened time-to-market/publication and product life cycles that prevail nowadays. This can only be achieved by the synthesis and examination of a large number of different materials developed by the systematic screening of a large parameter space of material constitution in a fast serial or parallel manner. Such an approach fuses the concepts of combinatorial material research and high-throughput experimentation (CMR/HTE)^[1] and is recently also understood as materials.^[2] The broad applicability of CMR/HTE technologies in discovery of novel as well as optimization of materials was comprehensively reviewed.^[3]

In this way application scenarios of CMR/HTE include applications when a high number of repetitive reactions with

only slight variations of reaction partners need to be performed to derive structure–property relationships or when these reactions need to be performed with high precision. However concerning the precision it needs to be considered that there may even be factors in the robotic setup like slight temperature variations of the reactors or different behavior of the dosing devices, which can result in systematic errors.^[4] Other application scenarios for CMR/HTE are those when only small amounts are required for initial hit identification, when the same reactions need to be performed several times to obtain sufficient statistical significance, e.g. when synthesized materials should be biologically evaluated, and last but not least when a high number of experiments need to be conducted within a limited time period.^[5]

Development by the combinatorial approach was first established for drug discovery in pharmaceutical industry^[6] and was then with an increasing number of applications also adapted to several other research fields like catalyst development,^[7] inorganic materials research^[8] as well as polymer chemistry in the last decade.^[9]

The actual term “combinatorial chemistry” is associated with the strict combination (i.e., chemical connection) of distinct compounds in every possible permutation. However, this term has been extended to all approaches that combine more than one

1. Introduction

Modern material research often faces the challenge that application derived requirements cannot be met by existing materials as modern materials need to be multifunctional and require many functions to be integrated. This cannot be fulfilled reasonably with materials developed by the classic approach of material

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Table 1. Examples for structural units and chemical entities in combinatorial chemistry.

Structural unit	Chemical entity	Discipline
Retrosynthetic molecule fragment	Small molecule	Pharmacology
Amino acid	Polypeptide	Proteomics
Nucleotide	RNA/DNA	Genomics
Monosaccharide	Glycans	Glycomics
Comonomer	Copolymer	Polymer materiomics
Polymer	Polymer blend	
Metal/metal oxide/-carbide/-nitride	Alloy/ceramic	Inorganic materiomics

Table 2. Differences between drug and material design.

	Drugs	Materials
Definition	Clear (e.g., sequence)	Very complex
Parameter space	Large (composition)	Very large (continuous, process-dependent properties)
Specificity	High (for biological receptor sites): yes/no criterion often applicable, hits easily defined	No or relatively low: results are scalars or even vectors, hit definition complex
Screening possibilities	Manifold as mixture or on solid supports	Most reliable results only as "pure", fully processed sample
Tolerance to impurities	High	Low/not acceptable

structural unit in an arbitrary manner to create a library of different chemical entities.

Examples for potential structural units and the corresponding chemical entities are listed in **Table 1**.

In material science and especially in polymer research the parameter space needs even to be extended as not only the sequence (or general composition) but also several other factors concerning the constitution of the material and the whole history of processing have an influence. Although in general the main idea of combinatorial material design is similar to drug design, the differences of both approaches are elucidated to distinguish between the different techniques of library synthesis, high-throughput screening (HTS), and hit identification.^[9a,10] **Table 2** summarizes the most important differences between drug and material design.

As this review concentrates on polymers and tries to give a glimpse of the almost endless parameter space for materials, the list in **Table 3** displays some potential parameters of polymeric materials.

Very early approaches of CMR by HTE were introduced by Hanak, in which a multisample concept in materials research was discussed.^[11] New superconducting materials were developed by multicomponent cosputtering of metals and ceramics to obtain substrates with a gradient library of the components that can be characterized very fast by nondestructive methods.

Table 3. Parameter space of polymers.

Parameters originated from...	
Control of polymerization reaction	Polymerization technique (used catalyst, initiator, solvent) Copolymer ratio(s) Molecular weights Molecular weight distribution
Formulation	Polymer architecture Composition of blends Additives: softeners, stabilizer, fillers, etc.
Processing	Thermal/mechanical history (processing temperature, annealing temperature, internal stress) Geometric factors (thickness, particle size, and distribution) Porosity (used porogene, pore size distribution, interconnectivity) Surface structure (e.g., roughness)
Postprocessing	Nature/density of surface-grafted groups Contact angle (surface energy) Leaching/extraction procedure

Although more than 40 years have passed, the main concept and the associated basic techniques are still state of the art.

In the following decades, the combinatorial approach for material development has gained more and more significance as many tools to accelerate synthesis and characterization became reliable, faster, and commercially available.^[10d,12] Especially the "bottlenecks" at the interfaces between material synthesis, processing, and characterization that seriously retarded HTE have been improved decisively. This could, e.g., be achieved by adopting the microwell plate standards and some of the general working techniques from biochemistry/cell biology, e.g., multichannel pipettes and plate readers. In addition, these efforts were accompanied by the trend to miniaturization—the 96-well plate standard was replaced by 384-well plates. The microwell format was proved as perfectly suited for automated operations (like plate reading or robotic liquid dispensing). Therefore, the next advance was obtained when robotic systems were introduced in CMR/HTE,^[13] which then led to the final breakthrough of the approach in polymer science in 2003.^[14] In the first instance these robotic systems replaced the experimenter in time-consuming process steps, e.g. volumetric dispensing.

Pioneers of CMR/HTE in the field of polymers are J. Kohn,^[15] J. C. Meredith (E. J. Amis),^[16] U. S. Schubert,^[17] and D. G. Anderson (R. Langer),^[18] which all focused on the combinatorial and high-throughput development of polymeric biomaterials.^[19]

An important advantage of polymers is the possibility to combine different functions to obtain so-called multifunctional materials. Dependent on the application the polymer research is aiming at, relevant functions which could be implemented by combinatorial and HTE were biocompatibility,^[10c,20] stimuli-sensitivity toward temperature^[21] or change of pH,^[21b] gene delivery,^[22] antioxidative,^[23] antifouling^[24] or antibacterial activity.^[25]

However, the more functions that need to be combined in such materials, the more complex is the finding of a suitable

Figure 1. Classification of polymer libraries.

composition of the polymeric construct. Therefore, combinatorial tools are highly relevant for developing multifunctional polymers. In this review we demonstrate how the concept of combinatorial polymer libraries combined with HTE experimentation substantially accelerates the research for new multifunctional polymers. While initially the value of HTE was the materials by itself, prepared in a standardized and automatized procedure, the field progressed to implement also the time-consuming characterization including function evaluation. Furthermore, first approaches for the automatized analysis of characterization data by the implantation of machine learning algorithms were demonstrated. Last but not least, by the coupling of HTE with 3D printing the digitalization of the materials itself could be demonstrated.

2. Methods of High-Throughput and Combinatorial Studies

2.1. Polymer Libraries and Their Preparation

2.1.1. Definition and Overview of Types of Polymer Libraries

Polymer materials provide a wide range of different properties. Mechanical characteristics alone can range from very soft, e.g., hydrogels with elastic moduli of around 100 kPa (or even lower) to very hard, e.g. reinforced plastics with E-moduli up to 100 GPa. In this way the applicability of these materials ranges as well. Of special interest is the field of smart, multifunctional polymers,^[18,26] i.e., materials that 1) fulfill more than one function, e.g., coatings (scratch protection, corrosion protection, high brilliance, etc.) and 2) are also stimuli-responsive, i.e., they provide a certain function only upon activation of internal/external triggers (e.g., shape, mechanical properties, release behavior, etc. upon alteration of temperature, magnetic field intensity, pH etc.).^[27] Knowledge-based approaches for the rational design of such materials would be very favorable for tailoring these func-

tions. However, even though minor correlations between the structure and the properties of the materials are well understood, the big picture of all interactions especially with cells in a living organism still needs to be explored thoroughly, to finally obtain quantitative structure–properties relationships. This task can be approached by combinatorial material studies using polymer libraries.

Polymer libraries are results/representations of combinatorial polymer preparation strategies. It is irrelevant whether the polymers are 1) formed (from monomers/prepolymers), 2) combined (with other polymers, additives, etc.), or 3) processed (with different parameters) during the combinatorial step. In literature these libraries are often divided into “synthesis libraries” and “formulation libraries”.^[9a] In addition to this classification by process we also propose the classification by spatial resolution of the polymer library (Figure 1).

2.1.2. High-Throughput Synthesis of Polymer Libraries

The synthesis of nonresolved (“0D”) libraries (synthesis libraries) in a reasonable time interval (“high-throughput synthesis”) is in general accomplished by parallelizing a certain number of experiments. It is important to keep the procedures as simple as possible to minimize the experimental effort as well as the number of sources of error. Therefore, it is essential to select reaction techniques and procedures requiring a minimum of manual steps, especially few or even no work-up steps following the polymerization are favorable. In order to increase the number of members of polymer synthesis libraries and broaden the conclusion of a study it is necessary to include a large number of monomers (or generally combinatorial components), however, the effort for library synthesis will grow exponentially. Accordingly, most steps within synthesis procedures are performed by means of automated/robotic synthesizers. The variety, possibilities and applicability of commercially available automated synthesis platforms was reviewed comprehensively.^[5,28] An

Table 4. Established high-throughput polymerization techniques.

Technique	Polymers	Method/tools	Max. library size ^{a)}	Ref.
Anionic polymerization	Poly(olefin)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/vortex) and liquid handling system, manual transfer of samples to analysis device	8	[29]
Cationic ROP	Poly(2-oxazoline)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/reflux/vortex) and liquid handling system, manual transfer of samples to analysis device	40	[28a,30]
Catalytic ROP	Poly(ester)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/reflux/vortex) and liquid handling system, manual transfer of samples to analysis device; alternatively microtiter plates with magnetic stirring	48	[31]
ATRP	Poly(acrylate)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/reflux/vortex) and liquid handling system, incl. automated solid phase extraction, GPC interface for online measurements; alternatively microtiter plates with magnetic stirring	96	[32]
Polycondensation	Poly(ester)s/poly(carbonate)s	Manually/classic experimentation	112	[33]
Polyaddition	Poly(esterurethanes)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/reflux/vortex) and liquid handling system, partially automated handling of samples	96	[34]
RAFT	Poly(acrylate)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/reflux/vortex) and liquid handling system, GPC interface for online measurements	150	[21,32b,35]
NMP	Poly(olefin)s	Robotic platform with reactor arrays (heat/cool/vortex) and liquid handling system, manual transfer of samples to analysis device	384	[36]
Michael-type polyaddition	Poly(β -amino ester)s	Manual (parallel) experimentation using microtiter plates with magnetic stirring	2350	[22,37]
Photopolymerization (PET-RAFT)	Poly(dimethyl acrylamide)s	Vial arrays or well-plates, micropipettes, 560 nm light	96–364	[38]

^{a)} The maximum library size is mainly determined by the size of reaction vessels and the reaction volume, respectively.

overview of relevant established polymerization techniques for parallel polymer synthesis is presented in **Table 4**.

The employment of robotic systems for polymer synthesis was an important breakthrough for the field of CMR. In first instance as it has become realizable to consider the synthesis of hundreds or even thousands of polymers for combinatorial studies. Moreover, these syntheses can be done in a very reproducible manner. However, some issues of robotic synthesis need to be pointed out. Generally, robotic syntheses are considered as “parallel.” A closer look on the procedures reveals that these techniques are not “fully parallel”. While reactors (or in general wells) are normally treated as collective (temperature control, stirring, etc.), chemicals can only be sequentially dispensed (although this is partially compensated by multichannel pipettes/needle-heads). Especially in the case when more than one chemical needs to be dispensed, this factor can make a big difference and may affect the result of the synthesis considerably. In an extreme case, the first chemical is dispensed in all wells before the second chemical is handled. This means there is a certain minimum time period between the two dispensing steps that might also vary from well to well, which may not be compatible with the reaction applied in the synthesis procedure. In the other extreme case both chemicals are dispensed sequentially into each well. In this scenario, the first well might be operated hours before last well, especially when rinsing steps have to be included to avoid cross contamination of reagents. The procedures from the standard/serial synthesis have to be translated carefully to automated/parallel applications for the robotic platforms to obtain the intended results.

Beside the considerations regarding parallelism it is also important to emphasize that most of the automated polymer syntheses in literature are polymerizations in solution, even in those cases when bulk polymerization is the common procedure applied in classical experimentation. However, bulk polymerization is hardly applicable to date for several reasons. 1) Handling of high viscous starting materials (e.g., prepolymers) has not yet been fully established in literature although appropriate robotic tools are available (e.g., GDU-V and GDU-HV from Chemspeed Technologies^[39]). 2) Vortexing is the most applied agitation mode especially for reactor arrays; high viscous bulk polymerization mixtures cannot be homogenized sufficiently by vortexing. 3) Taking samples (e.g., for kinetic studies) is critical challenging or even impossible. 4) The resulting polymers may have to be removed from the reactors manually, which could be a bottleneck of the HT workflow.

The mismatch between sample preparation and start of the reaction could be addressed by the implementation of photopolymerization into the library synthesis procedure. In this way the reaction can be started on demand. Here especially photo-induced electron-transfer-RAFT (PET-RAFT) polymerizations need to be named. Starting from initial proof of experiment, in which an iridium-based catalyst fac-[Ir(ppy)₃] was used to induce the photopolymerization with a low-energy light-emitting-diode (1–4.8 W, λ_{max} 435 nm) various monomers like acrylates, methacrylates, or methacrylamides could be polymerized.^[40] By using multiwell plates (96 or 364) as well as oxygen tolerant PET-RAFT photocatalyst ZnTPP and a yellow LED important

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of (micro)array and 1D gradient.

polymerization parameters like degree of control over molecular weight or polymerization rate could be investigated in an HT approach. Applying the similar HT approach, polymer libraries could be created in which 3-arm and 4-arm star-shaped polymers were obtained from *N,N*-dimethylacrylamide.^[38]

In addition to the technical progress in robot and synthesis instrumentation there is substantial progress in the DOE for HT.^[41] While in the past initial target structures were based on literature studies and knowledge of previous experiments of the experimenter, model-based predictions have become a source for the DOE.^[42] A feedback driven DOE can be achieved by the implementation of machine learning algorithms to assist and accelerate synthesis and reaction partner planning by making use of the results of previous experiments.^[43] This requires that the data are accessible and in a format, which is applicable to the machine learning algorithms. First examples making use of such an approach could be demonstrated for the development of catalysts^[44] or conductive MOFs.^[45]

2.1.3. Selected Techniques for the Preparation of Spatially Resolved Polymer Libraries

The huge advantage of creating spatially resolved libraries is the possibility to address the different polymer constitutions by automatic/robotic devices and by this enable high-throughput characterization. An additional feature of such libraries is that they are often very small (e.g., a whole library on a microscope slide) so that they can be tested in whole, for instance, in cell culture systems, instead of testing the polymers in different compartments separately. This increases the reproducibility of the tests while the effort is decreased by far.^[46]

The main distinction in the category of spatially resolved polymer libraries can be made between arrays and gradients (Figure 1). Arrays are libraries with a discrete, regular arrangement of (homogenous) polymer samples while in gradients constitutions/properties change in continuous fashion spatially (Figure 2).

The important advantages and disadvantages of arrays and gradients are summarized in Table 5. Both methods benefited in recent time by the implementation photopolymerization into the synthesis procedures to generate those libraries.

Techniques for the Preparation of Array Libraries: There are two main techniques to generate polymer library microarrays—ink-

Table 5. Advantages (+) and disadvantages (–) of arrays and gradients.

	Arrays		Gradients
+	Composition, etc., of every well is known	–	Composition, etc., has to be determined for hits in an additional step
–	Low information density (proportional to production time)	+	High information density (without increased effort)
+	Composition, etc., intentionally adjusted	–	Composition, etc., can only be influenced indirectly
–	Time consuming/expensive equipment	+	Comparatively easy preparation/low costs

Figure 3. Contact and ink-jet printing of microarrays with metal pins and nozzles. Reproduced with permission.^[20a] Copyright 2010, Elsevier.

jet and contact printing (Figure 3). Both techniques and other concepts were reviewed with a focus on multifunctional polymer development.^[20a,47] The general concept for combinatorial studies using microarrays (generated either by ink-jet or contact printing) is to combine different mono- to multifunctional monomers (predominately acrylates) by overprinting on the substrate and polymerize them in situ (often by photopolymerization).

In the common case, monomers, mixtures of monomers (and additives incl. solvents) or polymer solutions are transferred to flat substrates (mainly glass slides) that were surface treated before (e.g., to avoid non-specific cell adhesion on the substrate surface or to enhance material–substrate adhesion). The droplets (with diameters in the range from 50 to 300 μm) are then polymerized in situ or dried to form a solid material tightly connected to the substrate. Commonly at least one of the monomer components is a crosslinking agent to increase the rate of polymerization and to form networks (or gels, respectively) that can easily be extracted to remove residual monomers, which otherwise would adulterate continuing measurements.

Both techniques have advantages and disadvantages, however, ink-jet printing is emphasized to be the more versatile technique while contact printing is more facile and reliable, e.g., with the ink-jet technique, even living cells,^[48] proteins,^[49] and complex multicomponent constructs (by the additive manufacturing approach^[50]) can be printed. Table 6 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of the two techniques.

Table 6. Advantages (+) and disadvantages (–) of ink-jet and contact printing for combinatorial material research.

Ink-jet printing		Contact printing	
–	Complex droplet forming mechanism	+	Simple/reliable transfer mechanism
+	Material amount controllable (number of droplets)	+/-	Material amount control limited
+	Living cells, etc., can be printed	–	Living cell transfer problematic
–	Rinsing of complex system for material change is time consuming	+	Pins can easily be rinsed, frequent and fast material change possible

An overview of the ink-jet printing technology and of available commercial platforms is given by Schubert.^[51] The three important approaches are 1) classical printing using polymer solutions as inks, which are dried physically afterward,^[52] 2) in situ polymerization using monomers (or solutions of monomers), which are polymerized in an additional step after printing,^[53] and 3) reactive printing using two (or more) monomers that readily polymerize upon over-printing.^[54] The amount of ink and the composition, respectively, may be adjusted by the number of droplets for each spot, which is an important advantage for combinatorial studies. The combination of ink-jet printing with microfluidic gradient creation (see below) enhanced the digitalization of the HTE substantially.

Contact printing as a technology platform for multiplexed biological tests was introduced by Langer.^[18] Monomers are transferred to substrates and spots are photopolymerized immediately after deposition to avoid spreading of the drops and monomer evaporation, respectively, by inclusion of an UV lamp into the robotic system. The amount of monomers and their ratio may be adjusted in a limited extent by the number of transfers (multiple deposition). Alternatively, polymer solutions (prepared from synthesis libraries) may be transferred by contact printing to form arrayed libraries.^[55]

Techniques for the Preparation of Gradient Libraries: Techniques for gradient formation are combined with techniques of polymer film formation in subsequent or simultaneous manner to generate bulk gradient libraries (i.e., polymer films) (Table 7).

Table 7. Techniques for the preparation of bulk gradient libraries.

	Technique	Description/mechanism
Gradient formation	(Micro-)fluidic gradient generation	Successive mixing of two polymer solutions while mixture is withdrawn and/or deposited in stripes
	Convection-driven microfluidic mixing	Back and forward-pumping of two fluid flows within a microfluidic channel
	Temperature gradient	Polymers and polymer mixtures are annealed onto a temperature gradient
Film formation	Solution casting	Evaporation of solvent/lyophilization
	Photopolymerization	Crosslinking by (radical) polymerization

This in general means that gradients are formed and fixed.

The two important fluidic techniques, (micro-)fluidic gradient generation^[56] and convection-driven microfluidic mixing (CDMM)^[57] may either be combined with solution casting or photopolymerization to form compositional gradients. In the first case, either classic gradient maker or microfluidic devices are used (Figure 4). Classic gradient makers continuously mix both components, i.e., gradients are obtained in a temporal course, which are translated to a spatial gradient by continuous withdrawal of the solution and deposition. By contrast, microfluidic devices directly generate spatial gradients by stepwise separation and remixing of the fluids in a progressive manner (Figure 4C).

CDMM bases upon the dispersion effect, a combination of primary stretching by flow shear and secondary spreading by diffusion. This is done by back and forward pumping of two fluid plugs within a microfluidic channel (Figure 5).^[61] This way centimeter long compositional gradients can be generated in a very short time.

By thermal annealing of polymer films (consisting of either one polymer type or a blend) onto temperature gradients constitutional gradients are formed.^[62] The mobility of the polymer chains increases with increasing temperature, which leads to a

Figure 4. Schemes of (micro-)fluidic gradient creation: two types of classic gradient makers A (Adapted with permission.^[58] Copyright 2005, Elsevier) and B (Adapted with permission.^[59] Copyright 2003, John Wiley and Sons) and microfluidic gradient formation C (Reproduced with permission.^[60] Copyright 2004, American Chemical Society).

Figure 5. Scheme of convection-driven microfluidic mixing. Adapted with permission.^[57] Copyright 2010, John Wiley and Sons.

higher crystallinity or phase segregation of the polymer (blend) at the hot side of the temperature gradient. This way, different surface properties (e.g., topographies) can be introduced in gradient fashion.

By application of the concepts applied for 1D gradients in orthogonal fashion (esp. compositional and temperature gradients) 2D gradients can be obtained^[63] containing a significantly higher information density.

In contrast to bulk gradient libraries surface-bound gradients are generated when specific chemical moieties are anchored to the polymer surface (or generally) substrate in a gradual fashion.^[64] **Table 8** summarizes the most important techniques to generate surface-bound gradient libraries.

Plasma treatment of polymers leads to the generation of hydrophilic groups on the surface, mainly oxygen species, which increase the wettability of the surface.^[65] Two different techniques can be employed to generate gradients—radio-frequency plasma discharge (RFPD) and radio-frequency corona discharge (RFCD). In general, the wettability increases with the duration of treatment until saturation is reached.^[65] In case of RFPD, the gradients are generated by a partial shielding of the polymer surface with a mask, which is pulled apart with appropriate speed during the process (**Figure 6**, top). In case of RFCD gradients are obtained by the controlled translation of the polymer sample beneath the knife-type electrode (**Figure 6**, bottom).

Gradients of surface-grafted polymers open even more possibilities for combinatorial studies compared to simple surface

Figure 6. Schematic of radio frequency plasma discharge (top, a,b) and radio frequency corona discharge (bottom). Reproduced with permission.^[64c] Copyright 2008, Elsevier, (top) originally from ref. [66], reproduced with permission. Copyright 1990, The Polymer Society of Korea and (bottom) originally from ref. [67]. Reproduced with permission. Copyright 1992, Elsevier.

modification described above as not only the density and quality of the attached polymers can be varied but also the molecular weight. The vital process of every grafting-from technique is the activation of the surface and the introduction of reactive groups, respectively. This can be achieved by corona discharge to form gradients of radicals for a subsequent free radical polymerization of acrylates.^[68] The initial step for ATRP-based grafting-from techniques is to immobilize a gradient of initiator on the surface of flat silica substrates by a vapor diffusion/deposition process.^[69] In the subsequent living polymerization gradients of the grafting density, the molecular weight of the grafted polymers or chemistries (even different block lengths of block copolymers) can be realized, even as 2D gradients (molecular weight and grafting density).^[70] The complementary grafting-to approach is rather uncommon. The general key step for that is the immobilization of anchorage groups on the surface of the substrate, which is subsequently treated with (a solution) of the polymer containing the according counter groups. Examples are epoxide-modified silicon substrates and carboxyl-terminated

Table 8. Techniques for the preparation of surface-bound gradient libraries.

Method	Techniques	Mechanism	Typical substrates
Plasma treatment	Radio-frequency plasma discharge (RFPD) radio-frequency corona discharge (RFCD)	Introduction of (mainly) oxygen species (wettability gradients)	Poly(ethylene), poly(propylene), poly(ethylene terephthalate), poly(methyl methacrylate)
Polymer grafting	Grafting-from	Radical polymerization (free or ATRP) from the surface	Poly(ethylene), silica, silicon
	Grafting-to	Immobilization of anchorage groups, treatment with polymers with according counter groups	

Figure 7. Compositional maps of a 10 × 10 microwell library. Reproduced with permission.^[81] Copyright 2005, American Chemical Society.

polystyrene, poly(ethylene glycol)^[71] or poly(2-vinylpyridine),^[72] and also PLLA substrates, which are aminolyzed with hexanediamine and subsequently treated with glutaraldehyde and collagen.^[73] In grafting-to approaches, the gradient is often formed at a temperature gradient. At low temperatures the polymer chain mobility is low and therefore only low grafting densities are obtained; at high temperatures, however, high grafting densities can be realized. Combinations of both grafting approaches (grafting-from and grafting-to) also exist, for example, thiol-ene-based polymerization, which is carried out on and above the surface of a thiol-terminated self-assembled monolayer (SAM). Gradient materials are obtained by application of SAMs with a gradient in concentration of the surface bound thiol groups.^[74] Recently the PET-RAFT polymerization technique could also be applied as surface-initiated PET-RAFT (SI-PET-RAFT) to create surface-tethered chain-transfer agents.^[75] Various photocatalysts, monomers, and wavelengths were demonstrated to yield libraries of uniform polymer brush layers, block copolymer brush layers, and sophisticated topographically and chemically patterned surfaces.

2.2. High-Throughput Characterization of Polymer Libraries

High-throughput characterization of polymer libraries is a vital point for every CMR/HTE study. Here it needs to be considered that the number of samples generated per day does not exceed those that can be characterized in the same time when piling of samples should be avoided. This is of special importance for spatially nonresolved polymer libraries where manual handling often is not avoidable. In these cases it makes more sense to decrease the throughput in material synthesis to adapt to the throughput of the characterization process to end up in a continuous HT workflow.

It is important to distinguish between different modes of analyses. 1) Monitoring is the general term for the assessment of a process and the measurement of important parameters over time. Real-time monitoring, however, can only be done with special techniques that do not interfere with the running process, i.e., that the assessment is performed within the same vessel (by probes)^[76] or by noncontacting/spectroscopic techniques^[77] and not by taking samples. However, this is a rather rare case. 2)

In situ characterization implies the analysis of the sample at the designated position without the need of transferring it. 3) Online characterization implies the performance of the characterization parallel to the process,^[78] analysis samples are (automatically) taken and directly fed to the analysis device, i.e., samples are not collected before they are analyzed. 4) Multiplexed analyses comprise all tests where data acquisition of many (at least two) samples is performed in parallel fashion. This is generally realized by material arrays (microarrays or microtiter plates) in combination with sensor arrays^[79] and/or imaging techniques (FTIR microscopes) that directly deliver compositional maps (Figure 7).^[80]

Table 9 gives an overview of HT characterization techniques for the examination of bulk, surface and thermomechanical properties of polymers.

2.2.1. Selected Techniques for the High-Throughput Characterization of Molecular and Bulk Properties

Relevant molecular and bulk properties of polymeric materials are the composition, molecular weight, thermal, and thermomechanical properties. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) are widely applied for the determination of the composition of polymers. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) is a common method to investigate the molecular weight and distribution thereof. Thermal and thermomechanical properties of polymeric materials are of high relevance for the intended application scenarios of the polymers. Nanoindentation (NI) and dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) examine the behavior of polymers under quasi-static loading conditions while impact tests give information about the behavior of polymers under highly dynamic loading conditions. Therefore, high-throughput approaches for FTIR, NMR, GPC, NI, DMTA, and impact tests will be highlighted here.

FTIR and NMR are nowadays indispensable techniques for the qualitative as well as quantitative characterization of polymers. FTIR is used to identify (by the characteristic frequencies in the spectra) and quantify (by intensity of the signals) substances (or moieties). Of particular interest for polymer characterization are the mid-infrared range (MIR, 400–4000 cm⁻¹, containing primarily fundamental molecular vibrations) and the near-infrared

Table 9. Methods for the high-throughput characterization of polymer (libraries).

	Method (Abbr.)	Real-time	In situ	Measured properties	Advantages	Disadvantages	Ref.
bulk	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)	Y	Y	Concentration/composition	Fast qualitative/quantitative analysis	complex data interpretation	[28e]
	Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR)	N	Y	Concentration/composition	Powerful method to explore chemistries	Expensive equipment	[82]
	Gel permeation chromatography (GPC)	N	N	Molecular weight/distribution	Valuable method for the determination of molecular weight/distribution	Sample preparation necessary (polymer solution needed)	[83]
	Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time of flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-ToF)	N	N	Molecular weight/distribution	Mass spectral analysis of high molecular weight species (polymers, biomolecules)	Complex sample preparation, highly biased by sample history	[28a,84]
Surface	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)	N	Y	Surface chemistry	Powerful method, ToF-SIMS complement	Complex/expensive devices, data interpretation critical	[85]
	Time of flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS)	N	Y	Surface chemistry	Powerful method, XPS complement	Complex/expensive devices, data interpretation critical	[85]
	Water contact angle measurements (WCA)	N	Y	Wettability/surface energy	Cheap, fast, and easy method	Large samples with sufficient quality necessary	[55a,86]
	Atomic force microscopy (AFM)	N	Y	Surface topology, hardness	Cheap, easy, and automated method	Slow and only for small sample areas, artefacted (nonlinearity, hysteresis, creep, tip geometry)	[87]
	Surface plasmon resonance (SPR)	Y	Y	Adsorption	High sensitivity (biomolecules)	Expensive, limited applicability	[88]
Thermomechanical	Nanoindentation (NI)	N	Y	Hardness	Mechanical properties of small/thin samples	No information about ultimate strength	[80a,89]
	Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA)	N	N	Viscoelasticity	Facile method, covers a wide range of mechanical properties	Time consuming, expensive automation	[90]
	High-throughput mechanical characterization (HTMECH)	N	Y	Dynamic impact behavior	Direct mechanical characterization of (gradient) polymer libraries (films)	Sample preparation necessary, complex deformation mode (comparability critical)	[91]

range (NIR, 4000–12 500 cm^{-1} , containing primarily molecular overtone and combination vibrations).^[92] While MIR spectra generally are easier to be interpreted, NIR spectra provide more versatile information, which makes them suitable for sophisticated applications like structure elucidation (incl. molecular weight determination) of bio-derived macromolecules, e.g., polysaccharides, esp. chitosan and hyaluronic acid.^[93]

The most important modes for FTIR spectroscopy in HTS (**Table 10**) are transmission (trans-FTIR), attenuated total reflection (ATR-FTIR), reflection-absorption (FT-IRRAS), and diffuse reflection (DRIFT).

HT is achieved by employing multiwell sample holders for the automated read-out of libraries in a fast/unattended serial manner^[97] or by FTIR microscopes providing spatially resolved spectra.^[98] The latter are therefore especially useful for spatially resolved polymer libraries.

All modes of FTIR spectroscopy are mainly employed to examine the composition of polymer libraries, either consisting of

copolymers^[99] or polymer blends.^[100] The main concept for these examinations is assignment of signals within the NIR range to certain moieties of the components and the determination of the ratio of the components on the basis of normalized peak heights or areas.

Alternatively, the NIR range may be considered for a multivariate calibration using values obtained by means of complementary methods, e.g., by employing a robotic synthesizer platform four different methyl methacrylate-based polymer libraries with styrene, *N*-vinylpyrrolidone, 4-vinylpyridine, or 2-carboxyethyl acrylate as comonomers were synthesized. In a first step, the comonomer content was determined by means of ¹H-NMR. Using multivariate data analysis the obtained data were correlated with FTIR spectra of the copolymers determined via DRIFT spectroscopy (**Figure 8**). From these correlations, models for the prediction of the polymer composition on the basis of the DRIFT spectra could be generated and were verified in cross validation experiments subsequently. Moreover, in external validation

Table 10. Modes for FTIR spectroscopy.

Mode	Principle	Advantages	Disadvantages	Ref.
trans-FTIR 	IR radiation passes through the sample	Simple equipment, provides high-quality spectra	Sample preparation necessary	[94]
ATR-FTIR 	IR radiation is totally reflected on the interphase between ATR crystal and sample	No special sample preparation necessary, provides high-quality spectra	Possible bias (wave length dependent)	[95]
FT-IRRAS 	IR radiation passes through the sample and is reflected by (metal) support	Suitable for very thin layers (Ångström range)	Complex additional equipment necessary	[96]
DRIFT 	IR radiation is diffusely reflected by rough/powder sample	No sample preparation necessary	Biased spectra, broad signals	[97]

Figure 8. Scheme representing the workflow for the correlative characterization of polymer samples by DRIFT and $^1\text{H-NMR}$. Reproduced with permission.^[97] Copyright 2014, Wiley-VCH GmbH.

experiments the new methods were applied to independently synthesized sublibraries to test the practical application of models in a realistic environment. Only samples that were not identified as statistical outliers by the data analysis software were considered for the external validation. The average deviation of all methods was determined to be about 1–2 mol%. This way

and by application of commercially available high-throughput robotic synthesis platforms hundreds of polymer samples may be analyzed within a few hours.^[97]

Among the characterization methods of organic substances, NMR is one of the most powerful techniques. Therefore NMR is often used as master method for comparison/calibration of other characterization methods (e.g., FTIR).^[101] The potential of NMR for the characterization of polymers has been discussed elsewhere.^[102] Here, we point out some recent advances in the context of high-throughput characterization of polymers. The implementation of automated analysis can speed up the evaluation of NMR spectra.^[103] Of particular interest is solid-state NMR (SS-NMR) as polymers can be directly analyzed without the need to dissolve them, which would destroy possible supramolecular structures or other morphological features that eventually are scope of the examination.

Cross-polarization magic angle spinning (CP/MAS) NMR is an established technique for SSNMR to elucidate the molecular structure of porous polymer networks.^[104] However, acquisition times often exceed hours or even days, which makes them hardly compatible with any HT workflow. By dynamic nuclear polarization (DNP) SSNMR the sensitivity of the measurements can be increased and acquisition times decreased as less scans are sufficient for an acceptable signal/noise ratio.^[105] This way the HT structural analysis of polymer networks was enabled.^[82a] With the knowledge that FTIR measurements could be successfully adapted to investigate the composition of gradients, it was an ambition to also establish spatially resolved NMR for polymer libraries. This could be achieved by shifting the gradient

Figure 9. Schematic setup for a spatially resolved (1D) NMR: the gradient sample is moved through the stationary coil. Reproduced with permission.^[82b] Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society.

polymer library consisting of crosslinked poly(urethane) through the radio-frequency coil of an SSNMR device (**Figure 9**).^[82b] However, this method has only a limited resolution owing to the active range of the radio-frequency coil (centimeter scale).

With respect to polymer science, the determination of the molecular weight of polymers is just as important as the determination of the composition. GPC is the standard method to determine molecular weights and dispersities of polymers in solution^[106] and is especially very powerful in combination with viscosimetry and light scattering. In GPC the throughput in the analysis of samples is increased by usage of special HT columns with decreased particle diameter and/or reduced column length, which can also be operated at higher flow rates^[83a,83b] and by injecting samples before the whole analyte has passed the column (overlapping injections).^[107] By fine-tuning of the components of the GPC system analysis times can further be reduced whereby loss of separation quality remains acceptable.^[83c] For example, in a library of well-defined multiblock copolymers (MBC) composed of two different hydrophobic, semicrystalline blocks providing domains with well-separated melting temperatures (T_m) synthesized from the same type of precursor building blocks as strictly alternating (MBC_{alt}) or random (MBC_{ran}) MBC, the influence of starting composition on the molecular weight of the MBC was demonstrated.^[34] The three different series of MBCs_{alt} or MBCs_{ran} were synthesized by coupling oligo(ϵ -caprolactone) (OCL) of different molecular weights (2, 4, and 8 kDa) with oligotetrahydrofuran (OTHF, 2.9 kDa) via Steglich esterification in which the molar ratio of the reaction partners was slightly adjusted. In case of MBCs_{alt}, the highest molecular weight was achieved when a dicarboxylic acid content of 95 mol% was used. When MBCs_{ran} were designed, the optimum in M_w was realized with a slight increase in diCOOH mol% between 100 and 105 mol% (dependent on the chain length of OCL building blocks) (**Figure 10**).

Along with the increase of throughput of GPC measurements by instrumental measures, the bottleneck between polymer synthesis and characterization needs to be addressed. A reasonable approach is the usage of the robotic synthesizer to take and prepare samples automatically and directly transfer them into vials

of the autosampler of the GPC system.^[30b,107] More sophisticated but also more elaborated is the integration of an instrumental interphase into robotic synthesizer platforms for an online measurement,^[29a,32b] especially in combination with online-GC, which is of particular value for studying the kinetics of polymerization reactions.^[28a,78]

In addition to the composition and molecular weight, the analysis of thermal properties of (multiblock)copolymers is of critical relevance as from these measurements first indications for the morphology of the polymer system can be obtained. While measurement of the thermal conductivity could be adopted to high-throughput approaches as demonstrated for alloys within the material genome project,^[108] the high-throughput determination of thermal transitions via differential scanning calorimetry is still a challenge. A certain automated processing can be realized by DSC systems operated with automated sampling systems, including the automated punching devices for the DSC pans. No clear influence on the thermal transitions was observed for the MBC discussed above as function of the M_w . In case of polyurethanes with OCL building blocks, a distinct reduction of melting transitions were obtained when the overall M_w was increased, which was attributed to the strong hydrogen bonds interfering with the crystallization of oligomers and therefore reducing T_m . Interestingly, the thermal transitions were slightly affected by the sequence structure of MBC. It was concluded that the T_m s of the random series were in most cases slightly higher compared to T_m s of the alternating series and was attributed to the crystallization process, which could be suppressed by a hindered phase segregation when OCL and OTHF are polymerized in an alternating structure (**Figure 11**). However, depending on the temperature range in which the thermal transitions are expected and the temperature program (e.g., 1st heating run for erasing the thermal history, cooling run, 2nd heating run) the amount of liquid nitrogen for cooling can be quite high and limit the automated processing to a few samples until the liquid nitrogen tank needs to be refilled.

In order to be able to tailor the mechanical properties of polymers for the final application it is important to study structure-properties relationships of these material parameters by combinatorial methods. NI is an established high-throughput examination method for the mechanical behavior of polymers^[89a] and was easily adapted for gradient^[80a] and microarray^[89b] polymer libraries. In NI sample positions are defined and the measurements can be performed in an automated manner. The elastic as well as plastic deformation of very small samples can be examined and typical values (e.g., the modulus) can be determined by an instrumented penetration test (**Figure 12**) using indentation tips with defined geometry.^[89a]

However, NI cannot determine all relevant mechanical properties, esp. strengths are not accessible. Therefore other techniques were developed. An example is a tool for the high-throughput dynamic impact characterization of polymer films (HTMECH).^[91a] The tool enabled HT measurements by clamping polymer films between two perforated steel plates and the freestanding film sections could subsequently automated impact tested with a hemispherical contact tip in a fast serial manner (**Figure 13**).

This technique was esp. adapted to the format of the 2D gradient libraries.^[91b] A similar technique was also introduced in a

Figure 10. Weight average molecular weight of MBCs with a) an alternating (MBC_{ait}) and b) random sequence structure (MBC_{ran}) as function of the chain length of the OCL building block and molar ratio of die dicarboxylic acid groups. Molecular weight of the PCL precursor: I) 2 k, II) 4 k, III) 8 k. Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY 4.0 license.^[34] Copyright 2021, The authors, published by Elsevier.

commercial platform for parallel DMTA of polymer films^[90b] to enable the HT acquisition of viscoelastic properties of polymeric materials.

As an example, the influence of the OCL weight content on the complex modulus $|E^*|$ is depicted in **Figure 14** for the library of MBC described above. It can be noticed that although the OCL weight content of MBC_{ran} is lower compared to MBC_{ait} , higher moduli were obtained. This finding was a first indicator that in the random MBC a better phase segregation can occur, which enables, e.g., more crystalline domains to act as physical crosslinks. These findings could be supported by wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) measurements. The crystal sizes determined for OTHF phase ranged between 6.1 and 20.2 nm and were not affected by M_w of MBC, but were highly dependent on the chain length of OCL and on the sequence structure of MBC. Here, the lateral crystal size l_c of OTHF decreased from about 19.2 ± 0.8 nm for ranOCL(2k)OTHF to 9.2 ± 0.9 nm for ranOCL(8k)OTHF. This reduction was attributed to the reduced content of OTHF (52–56 wt% OTHF in OCL(2k)OTHF and 23–26 wt% OTHF in OCL(8k)OTHF) integrated in MBC when the chain length of OCL

building blocks was increased. Although these measurements were WAXS investigations were not performed as HT experiments, suitable modification of the instrumental setup enables also HT WAXS measurements.^[110]

2.2.2. Selected Techniques for the High-Throughput Characterization of Surface Properties

Functional groups on the surface as well as the structure/morphology of the surface are relevant methods to characterize the interface of polymers to biological systems (proteins and cells), which first recognize the surface of any material. The surface characterization methods discussed in this review include X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, also ESCA, electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis), time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS), and water contact angle (WCA) measurements (**Figure 15**).^[85]

XPS provides information about the quantitative elemental composition of the surface.^[111] Hence, it is primarily employed

Figure 11. Melting temperatures (T_m) of MBCs determined from the second heating run of DSC measurements as a function of molecular weights. a) OTHF domains and b) OCL domains. Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY 4.0 license.^[34] Copyright 2021, The authors, published by Elsevier.

Figure 12. Indentation load–displacement curve: the elastic modulus is derived from the stiffness (S^*). Reproduced with permission.^[89a] Copyright 2001, John Wiley and Sons.

Figure 13. Schematic of high-throughput impact test (HTMECH). Reproduced with permission.^[91c] Copyright 2005, AIP Publishing.

to verify whether the surface has the intended composition^[112] before, e.g., further experiments are conducted with this surface. Under ultrahigh vacuum (around 10^{-8} mbar), the samples are irradiated with X-rays, which excite the atoms at the surface (10 nm, about 20 atom layers) and cause the emittance of photoelectrons upon relaxation. The kinetic energy of the photoelectrons refers to the binding energy, which is related to the specific element while the number of electrons is directly related to the amount of the according element. HT is enabled by employing the imaging mode of modern XPS devices, where large samples (microarray chips) may be scanned in a single acquisition run. XPS was employed in studies for the prediction of biologic response in combination with other complementary methods.^[113] A critical aspect of XPS is the interpretation of the received data as the signal intensity is element specific and has to be corrected and normalized for quantitative evaluation. Hydrogen cannot be detected and therefore it is not considered in the calculated atomic percentages. Charged surfaces lead to a shift of the binding energy of the electrons, which has to be kept in mind when peaks are assigned to certain elements. XPS is generally handled as a non-destructive technique. However, high energy

bremsstrahlung, the heating of the sample during analysis, and the evaporation of volatile components might change the structure of the material and adulterate the results.

In case of ToF-SIMS, a pulsed beam of ions (generally Bi_3^+) sputters through the surface of the samples under ultrahigh vacuum and the released secondary ions are analyzed by a time-of-flight mass spectrometer. Hence, ToF-SIMS delivers qualitative mass spectrometric information of the top monolayer of the examined material^[111] and is considered as a valuable complementary technique to XPS.^[114] Again data interpretation is critical as secondary ion formation is very complex. Nevertheless, ToF-SIMS already found wide-spread application in biomaterial sciences decades ago.^[115] Recently ToF-SIMS has gained attention in combination with multivariate statistical methods like

Figure 14. Complex moduli $|E^*|$ of MBC as a function of temperature, OCL weight content, and chain length of OCL building blocks. Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY license.^[109] Copyright 2021, Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht, published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

Figure 15. High-throughput surface characterization methods. Reproduced with permission.^[20a] Copyright 2010, Elsevier.

principal component analysis and partial least squares regression as it enables prediction of important properties, e.g., surface energy.^[116] Moreover, by spatial resolution in combination with imaging methods compositional maps can be generated, which enables the examination of chemical heterogeneities of arrayed polymer libraries in HT.^[117]

WCA measurements have a tremendous value for the characterization of the interface as WCA is related to the surface en-

ergy, which influences the protein and cell attachment.^[118] Accordingly, it was particularly important to perform WCA measurements in a high-throughput mode. This was achieved by a robotic dispensing of water drops, and an automated photographing and image analysis for automated data evaluation. WCA can either be derived from the spreading area of the drop at constant volume^[55a] or by direct image processing of the drop shape in profile (**Figure 16**).^[86] WCA measurements could be further

Figure 16. Automated water contact measurements by evaluation of droplet spreading area (top), (Reproduced with permission.^[55a] Copyright 2003, John Wiley and Sons) and droplet profile analysis (bottom) (Reproduced with permission.^[86] Copyright 2004, Wiley-VCH GmbH).

miniaturized to work with picoliter drops, which enabled even analysis of spatially resolved polymer libraries with dimensions below 100 μm .^[119]

3. Conclusion and Outlook

Combinatorial material development in combination with high-throughput experimentation accelerated research in the field of multifunctional polymers tremendously. Different tools to speed up the certain levels of material design were established and most of the devices therefore are nowadays commercially available. Important advances are robotic synthesis, HT modes of classical characterization methods and the employment of spatially resolved polymer libraries.

Relevant polymerization techniques were established for robotic platforms and thus are available for the HT synthesis of combinatorial synthesis libraries. Moreover, these robotic platforms enable the fully automated work-up of the polymers prepared after the polymerization procedures up to the preparation of samples provided in the autosampler rack for subsequent HT characterization or even by online-characterization employing an integrated interface to the HT analysis apparatus.

The concept of spatially resolved polymer libraries was adopted to increase throughput during the next steps of polymer design as these platforms enable multiplexed biological tests and a fast surface characterization avoiding the handling of individual samples. Although both highlighted platforms—microarray and gradient biomaterial libraries—share the possibilities for HTE, both differ in the nature and density of the information within the parameter space of the material system. While microarrays

generally contain polymers with a high chemical diversity, gradients include polymers with a high compositional/constitutional resolution. Relying on the concept of combinatorial drug design it is therefore reasonable to include microarrays in the early stage of a study to gather hit materials from a large pool of highly diverse materials. These hit materials may be refined by the multigeneration library strategy by the HT synthesis of a library with decreased diversity but increased compositional resolution. However, as soon as lead materials can be defined, it is advisable to switch over to gradients libraries to exploit the high compositional resolution of this concept. This proposed overall workflow concept (as shown in **Figure 17**) is not applicable to all material systems and studies, e.g., for on-chip synthesis of microarray libraries the separate HT synthesis/characterization steps are omitted.

However, this scheme combines relevant successful concepts in literature to one integrated HT workflow. With these tools in mind, we anticipate an ongoing increase, e.g., for the number of functions, which can be integrated into polymers to gain multifunctional materials. This becomes even more likely as the future of the CMT/HTE is directing into the integration and implementation of machine learning into the analysis HT data as well as in the DOE. In this way self-reinforcing systems for the synthesis and characterization of material databases are created. First approaches of such machine-learning based self-reinforcing synthesis could already be demonstrated in hybrid systems like MOFs.^[120] Machine-based optimization could also be shown for the fabrication of materials like solar cell materials.^[121] However, key requirements for such machine learning based HTE in addition to appropriate training sets are data libraries and storage environments.^[41]

Figure 17. Proposed high-throughput workflow for the combinatorial development of multifunctional polymers employing polymer libraries.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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- [1] N. Adams, U. S. Schubert, *QSAR Comb. Sci.* **2005**, 24, 58.
 [2] S. W. Cranford, J. de Boer, C. A. van Blitterswijk, M. J. Buehler, *Adv. Mater.* **2013**, 25, 802.
 [3] a) R. A. Potyrailo, K. Rajan, K. Stoewe, I. Takeuchi, B. J. Chisholm, H. Lam, *ACS Comb. Sci.* **2011**, 13, 579; b) E. Busseron, Y. Ruff, E.

Moulin, N. Giuseppone, *Nanoscale* **2013**, 5, 7098; c) K. Hadinoto, A. Sundaresan, W. S. Cheow, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* **2013**, 85, 427; d) L. Himanen, A. Geurts, A. S. Foster, P. Rinke, *Adv. Sci.* **2019**, 6, 1900808.

- [4] a) C. Guerrero-Sanchez, J. Zhang, J. Vitz, U. S. Schubert, *Encyclopedia of Polymer Science and Technology*, **2021**, <https://doi.org/10.1002/0471440264.pst668>; b) S. Baudis, M. Balk, A. Lendlein, M. Behl, *MRS Adv.* **2016**, 1, 2003.
 [5] S. Oliver, L. Zhao, A. J. Gormley, R. Chapman, C. Boyer, *Macromolecules* **2019**, 52, 3.
 [6] a) R. A. Goodnow, *J. Cell. Biochem.* **2001**, 84, 13; b) R. A. Houghten, *Annu. Rev. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* **2000**, 40, 273; c) H. Bienaymé, C. Hulme, G. Odon, P. Schmitt, *Chem. –Eur. J.* **2000**, 6, 3321; d) R. F. Service, *Science* **2015**, 347, 1190; e) J. Li, S. G. Ballmer, E. P. Gillis, S. Fujii, M. J. Schmidt, A. M. E. Palazzolo, J. W. Lehmann, G. F. Morehouse, M. D. Burke, *Science* **2015**, 347, 1221.
 [7] Z. Qun Zheng, X. Ping Zhou, *Comb. Chem. High Throughput Screening* **2011**, 14, 147.
 [8] a) M. Woodhouse, B. A. Parkinson, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, 38, 197; b) I. Takeuchi, in *Thin Films and Heterostructures for Oxide Electronics* (Eds: O. Auciello, R. Ramesh), Springer, Boston, MA **2005**, p. 333; c) J. Hulliger, M. Aslam Awan, B. Trusch, T. A. Samtleben, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* **2005**, 631, 1255.
 [9] a) J. C. Meredith, *J. Mater. Sci.* **2003**, 38, 4427; b) H. Zhang, R. Hoogenboom, M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **2005**, 16, 203; c) D. C. Webster, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, 209, 237; d) Y. Liu, J.-M. Lehn, A. K. H. Hirsch, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2017**, 50, 376.
 [10] a) A. Tuchbreiter, J. Marquardt, B. Kappler, J. Honerkamp, M. O. Kristen, R. Mulhaupt, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, 24, 47; b) J. N. Cawse, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2001**, 34, 213; c) A. K. Patel, M. W. Tibbitt,

- A. D. Celiz, M. C. Davies, R. Langer, C. Denning, M. R. Alexander, D. G. Anderson, *Curr. Opin. Solid State Mater. Sci.* **2016**, *20*, 202; d) K. Mitsudo, Y. Kurimoto, K. Yoshioka, S. Suga, *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 5985.
- [11] J. J. Hanak, *J. Mater. Sci.* **1970**, *5*, 964.
- [12] a) B. Jandeleit, D. J. Schaefer, T. S. Powers, H. W. Turner, W. H. Weinberg, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **1999**, *38*, 2494; b) Y. L. Dar, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 34; c) M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *Soft Matter* **2006**, *2*, 371; d) Y. Jin, Q. Wang, P. Taynton, W. Zhang, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *47*, 1575; e) B. M. Cooper, D. Putnam, *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **2016**, *2*, 1837.
- [13] a) S. Schmatloch, M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 33; b) S. Schmatloch, M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *G.I.T. Lab. J., Eur.* **2003**, *7*, 254.
- [14] U. S. Schubert, C. S. Kniep, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 13.
- [15] J. Kohn, W. J. Welsh, D. D. Knight, *Biomaterials* **2007**, *28*, 4171.
- [16] E. J. Amis, *Nat. Mater.* **2004**, *3*, 83.
- [17] U. S. Schubert, E. J. Amis, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 19.
- [18] D. G. Anderson, J. A. Burdick, R. Langer, *Science* **2004**, *305*, 1923.
- [19] a) S. Brocchini, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2001**, *53*, 123; b) J. R. Smith, A. Seyda, N. Weber, D. D. Knight, S. Abramson, J. Kohn, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 127; c) J. C. Meredith, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2009**, *19*, 34; d) C. G. J. Simon, S. Lin-Gibson, *Adv. Mater.* **2011**, *23*, 369; e) A. Peters, D. M. Brey, J. A. Burdick, *Tissue Eng., Part B* **2009**, *15*, 225.
- [20] a) A. L. Hook, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, P. Williams, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Biomaterials* **2010**, *31*, 187; b) F. Soheilmooghaddam, M. Rumble, J. Cooper-White, *Chem. Rev.* **2021**, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.0c01026>.
- [21] a) D. Fournier, R. Hoogenboom, H. M. L. Thijs, R. M. Paulus, U. S. Schubert, *Macromolecules* **2007**, *40*, 915; b) C. R. Becer, S. Hahn, M. W. M. Fijten, H. M. L. Thijs, R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2008**, *46*, 7138.
- [22] D. M. Lynn, D. G. Anderson, D. Putnam, R. Langer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 8155.
- [23] T. Mao, G. Liu, H. Wu, Y. Wei, Y. Gou, J. Wang, L. Tao, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, *140*, 6865.
- [24] A. Ekin, D. C. Webster, *J. Comb. Chem.* **2007**, *9*, 178.
- [25] a) A. L. Hook, C. Y. Chang, J. Yang, J. Luckett, A. Cockayne, S. Atkinson, Y. Mei, R. Bayston, D. J. Irvine, R. Langer, D. G. Anderson, P. Williams, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Nat. Biotechnol.* **2012**, *30*, 868; b) G. Liu, Q. Zhang, Y. Li, X. Wang, H. Wu, Y. Wei, Y. Zeng, L. Tao, *iScience* **2020**, *23*, 100754.
- [26] A. Lendlein, R. S. Trask, *Multifunct. Mater.* **2018**, *1*, 010201.
- [27] a) J. M. Karp, R. Langer, *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **2007**, *18*, 454; b) A. S. Hoffman, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2013**, *65*, 10; c) C. Löwenberg, M. Balk, C. Wischke, M. Behl, A. Lendlein, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2017**, *50*, 723; d) M. Bruneau, S. Bennis, J. Brendle, P. Dutournie, L. Limousy, S. Pluchon, *J. Controlled Release* **2019**, *294*, 355; e) P. Zarrintaj, M. Jouyandeh, M. R. Ganjali, B. S. Hadavand, M. Mozafari, S. S. Sheiko, M. Vatankeh-Varnoosfaderani, T. J. Gutiérrez, M. R. Saeb, *Eur. Polym. J.* **2019**, *117*, 402.
- [28] a) R. Hoogenboom, M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 15; b) R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2003**, *41*, 2425; c) M. A. R. Meier, R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 21; d) M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2004**, *14*, 3289; e) S. Schmatloch, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 69; f) C. Guerrero-Sanchez, U. S. Schubert, *Chem. Today* **2005**, *23*, 34; g) R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2005**, *76*, 062202; h) C. Guerrero-Sanchez, R. M. Paulus, M. W. M. Fijten, M. J. de la Mar, R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2006**, *252*, 2555; i) C. R. Becer, U. S. Schubert, M. A. R. Meier, D. C. Webster, *Adv. Polym. Sci.* **2009**, *225*, 17; j) V. Sans, L. Cronin, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2016**, *45*, 2032; k) A. W. Sun, S. Lackner, B. M. Stoltz, *Trends Chem.* **2019**, *1*, 630; l) Y. Shi, P. L. Prieto, T. Zepel, S. Grunert, J. E. Hein, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2021**, *54*, 546.
- [29] a) C. Guerrero-Sanchez, C. H. Abeln, U. S. Schubert, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2005**, *43*, 4151; b) C. Guerrero-Sanchez, D. Wouters, C.-A. Fustin, J.-F. Gohy, B. G. G. Lohmeijer, U. S. Schubert, *Macromolecules* **2005**, *38*, 10185.
- [30] a) F. Wiesbrock, R. Hoogenboom, M. A. M. Leenen, S. F. G. M. van Nispen, M. van der Loop, C. H. Abeln, A. M. J. van den Berg, U. S. Schubert, *Macromolecules* **2005**, *38*, 7957; b) R. Hoogenboom, F. Wiesbrock, M. A. M. Leenen, M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *J. Comb. Chem.* **2005**, *7*, 10; c) R. Hoogenboom, M. W. M. Fijten, S. Wijmans, A. M. J. van den Berg, H. M. L. Thijs, U. S. Schubert, *J. Comb. Chem.* **2006**, *8*, 145.
- [31] a) M. A. R. Meier, J.-F. Gohy, C.-A. Fustin, U. S. Schubert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2004**, *126*, 11517; b) A. Ekin, D. C. Webster, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2006**, *44*, 4880.
- [32] a) H. Zhang, M. W. M. Fijten, R. Hoogenboom, R. Reinierkens, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 81; b) H. Zhang, V. Marin, M. W. M. Fijten, U. S. Schubert, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2004**, *42*, 1876; c) H. Zhang, C. H. Abeln, M. W. M. Fijten, U. S. Schubert, *e-Polymers* **2006**, <https://doi.org/10.1515/epoly.2006.6.1.90>; d) M. J. Nasrullah, D. C. Webster, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2009**, *210*, 640; e) D. J. Siegwart, M. Leiendecker, R. Langer, D. G. Anderson, *Macromolecules* **2012**, *45*, 1254.
- [33] a) S. I. Ertel, J. Kohn, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.* **1994**, *28*, 919; b) S. Brocchini, K. James, V. Tangpasuthadol, J. Kohn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1997**, *119*, 4553; c) S. Brocchini, K. James, V. Tangpasuthadol, J. Kohn, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.* **1998**, *42*, 66; d) C. H. Reynolds, R. Druker, L. B. Pfahler, *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **1998**, *38*, 305; e) C. H. Reynolds, *J. Comb. Chem.* **1999**, *1*, 297; f) J. Rickerby, R. Prabhakar, A. Patel, J. Knowles, S. Brocchini, *J. Controlled Release* **2005**, *101*, 21.
- [34] M. Behl, M. Balk, K. Lützwang, A. Lendlein, *Eur. Polym. J.* **2021**, *143*, 110207.
- [35] a) R. M. Paulus, M. W. M. Fijten, M. J. de la Mar, R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *QSAR Comb. Sci.* **2005**, *24*, 863; b) C. R. Becer, A. M. Groth, R. Hoogenboom, R. M. Paulus, U. S. Schubert, *QSAR Comb. Sci.* **2008**, *27*, 977; c) M. W. M. Fijten, R. M. Paulus, U. S. Schubert, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2005**, *43*, 3831; d) P. Chapon, C. Mignaud, G. Lizarraga, M. Destarac, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 87; e) V. Kholodovych, A. V. Gubskaya, M. Bohrer, N. K. Harris, D. D. Knight, J. Kohn, W. J. Welsh, *Polymer* **2008**, *49*, 2435; f) J. Ghosh, D. Y. Lewitus, P. Chandra, A. Joy, J. Bushman, D. D. Knight, J. Kohn, *Polymer* **2011**, *52*, 2650; g) P. M. Kou, N. Pallasana, R. Bowden, B. Cunningham, A. Joy, J. Kohn, J. E. Babensee, *Biomaterials* **2012**, *33*, 1699.
- [36] a) A. W. Bosman, A. Heumann, G. Klaerner, D. Benoit, J. M. J. Fréchet, C. J. Hawker, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2001**, *123*, 6461; b) T. M. Eggenhuisen, C. R. Becer, M. W. M. Fijten, R. Eckardt, R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *Macromolecules* **2008**, *41*, 5132.
- [37] a) D. G. Anderson, C. A. Tweedie, N. Hossain, S. M. Navarro, D. M. Brey, K. J. Van Vliet, R. Langer, J. A. Burdick, *Adv. Mater.* **2006**, *18*, 2614; b) D. G. Anderson, D. M. Lynn, R. Langer, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2003**, *42*, 3153; c) D. G. Anderson, W. Peng, A. Akinc, N. Hossain, A. Kohn, R. Padera, R. Langer, J. A. Sawicki, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2004**, *101*, 16028; d) J. J. Green, G. T. Zugates, N. C. Tedford, C. L. Huang, L. G. Griffith, D. A. Lauffenburger, J. A. Sawicki, R. Langer, D. G. Anderson, *Adv. Mater.* **2007**, *19*, 2836; e) D. Jere, M.-K. Yoo, R. Arote, T.-H. Kim, M.-H. Cho, J.-W. Nah, Y.-J. Choi, C.-S. Cho, *Pharm. Res.* **2008**, *25*, 875.
- [38] A. J. Gormley, J. Yeow, G. Ng, Ó. Conway, C. Boyer, R. Chapman, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 1557.

- [39] Chemspeed-Technologies, Gravimetric Dispensing/Dosing Unit for (High) Viscous Liquids, www.chemspeed.com (accessed: June 2021).
- [40] J. Xu, K. Jung, A. Atme, S. Shanmugam, C. Boyer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 5508.
- [41] J. Kimmig, S. Zechel, U. S. Schubert, *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, *33*, 2004940.
- [42] *Nat. Mater.* **2016**, *15*, 365.
- [43] B. Sanchez-Lengeling, A. Aspuru-Guzik, *Science* **2018**, *361*, 360.
- [44] L. Banko, A. Ludwig, *ACS Comb. Sci.* **2020**, *22*, 401.
- [45] Y. He, E. D. Cubuk, M. D. Allendorf, E. J. Reed, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2018**, *9*, 4562.
- [46] Y. Mei, M. Goldberg, D. G. Anderson, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **2007**, *11*, 388.
- [47] a) L. Smith Callahan, *Gels* **2016**, *2*, 18; b) L. Yang, S. Pijuan-Galito, H. S. Rho, A. S. Vasilevich, A. D. Eren, L. Ge, P. Habibović, M. R. Alexander, J. de Boer, A. Carlier, P. van Rijn, Q. Zhou, *Chem. Rev.* **2021**, *121*, 4561.
- [48] a) C. Norotte, F. S. Marga, L. E. Niklason, G. Forgacs, *Biomaterials* **2009**, *30*, 5910; b) A. R. Liberski, J. T. Delaney, U. S. Schubert, *ACS Comb. Sci.* **2011**, *13*, 190.
- [49] J. T. Delaney, P. J. Smith, U. S. Schubert, *Soft Matter* **2009**, *5*, 4866.
- [50] B. Wendel, D. Rietzel, F. Kühnlein, R. Feulner, G. Hülder, E. Schmachtenberg, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2008**, *293*, 799.
- [51] B.-J. de Gans, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 659.
- [52] B.-J. de Gans, E. Kazancioglu, W. Meyer, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 292.
- [53] R. Zhang, A. R. Liberski, F. Khan, J. J. Diaz-Mochon, M. Bradley, *Chem. Commun.* **2008**, 1317.
- [54] P. Kröber, J. T. Delaney, J. Perelaer, U. S. Schubert, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2009**, *19*, 5234.
- [55] a) J.-F. Thaburet, H. Mizomoto, M. Bradley, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 366; b) M. Zeng, Y. Zhang, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, *7*, 23301.
- [56] J. C. Meredith, A. Karim, E. J. Amis, *Macromolecules* **2000**, *33*, 5760.
- [57] J. He, Y. Du, Y. Guo, M. J. Hancock, B. Wang, H. Shin, J. Wu, D. Li, A. Khademhosseini, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **2010**, *108*, 175.
- [58] S. A. DeLong, A. S. Gobin, J. L. West, *J. Controlled Release* **2005**, *109*, 139.
- [59] J. C. Meredith, J.-L. Sormana, B. G. Keselowsky, A. J. Garcia, A. Tona, A. Karim, E. J. Amis, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part A* **2003**, *66A*, 483.
- [60] J. A. Burdick, A. Khademhosseini, R. Langer, *Langmuir* **2004**, *20*, 5153.
- [61] Y. Du, M. J. Hancock, J. He, J. L. Villa-Urbe, B. Wang, D. M. Cropek, A. Khademhosseini, *Biomaterials* **2010**, *31*, 2686.
- [62] N. R. Washburn, K. M. Yamada, C. G. J. Simon, S. B. Kennedy, E. J. Amis, *Biomaterials* **2003**, *25*, 1215.
- [63] J. C. Meredith, A. P. Smith, A. Tona, H. Elgandy, A. Karim, E. J. Amis, *Polym. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **2001**, *84*, 1065.
- [64] a) T. G. Ruardy, J. M. Schakenraad, H. C. van der Mei, H. J. Busscher, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* **1997**, *29*, 3; b) J. Genzer, R. R. Bhat, *Langmuir* **2008**, *24*, 2294; c) M. S. Kim, G. Khang, H. B. Lee, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2008**, *33*, 138; d) S. Morgenthaler, C. Zink, N. D. Spencer, *Soft Matter* **2008**, *4*, 419.
- [65] J. H. Lee, J. W. Park, H. B. Lee, *Biomaterials* **1991**, *12*, 443.
- [66] J. H. Lee, J. W. Park, H. B. Lee, *Polymer* **1990**, *14*, 646.
- [67] J. H. Lee, H. G. Kim, G. S. Khang, H. B. Lee, M. S. Jhon, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **1992**, *151*, 563.
- [68] B. J. Jeong, J. H. Lee, H. B. Lee, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **1996**, *178*, 757.
- [69] a) T. Wu, M. R. Tomlinson, K. Efimenko, J. Genzer, *J. Mater. Sci.* **2003**, *38*, 4471; b) Y. Mei, T. Wu, C. Xu, K. J. Langenbach, J. T. Elliott, B. D. Vogt, K. L. Beers, E. J. Amis, N. R. Washburn, *Langmuir* **2005**, *21*, 12309; c) Y. Mei, J. T. Elliott, J. R. Smith, K. J. Langenbach, T. Wu, C. Xu, K. L. Beers, E. J. Amis, L. Henderson, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part A* **2006**, *79A*, 974.
- [70] R. R. Bhat, B. N. Chaney, J. Rowley, A. Liebmann-Vinson, J. Genzer, *Adv. Mater.* **2005**, *17*, 2802.
- [71] L. Ionov, B. Zdyrko, A. Sidorenko, S. Minko, V. Klep, I. Luzinov, M. Stamm, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 360.
- [72] L. Ionov, A. Sidorenko, M. Stamm, S. Minko, B. Zdyrko, V. Klep, I. Luzinov, *Macromolecules* **2004**, *37*, 7421.
- [73] H. Tan, L. Wan, J. Wu, C. Gao, *Colloids Surf., B* **2008**, *67*, 210.
- [74] V. S. Khire, D. S. W. Benoit, K. S. Anseth, C. N. Bowman, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2006**, *44*, 7027.
- [75] M. Li, M. Fromel, D. Ranaweera, S. Rocha, C. Boyer, C. W. Pester, *ACS Macro Lett.* **2019**, *8*, 374.
- [76] S. Shaikh, J. E. Puskas, G. Kaszas, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* **2004**, *42*, 4084.
- [77] R. A. Potyrailo, *Trends Anal. Chem.* **2003**, *22*, 374.
- [78] R. Hoogenboom, M. W. M. Fijten, C. H. Abeln, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 237.
- [79] a) R. A. Potyrailo, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 77; b) R. A. Potyrailo, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2006**, *45*, 702.
- [80] a) C. G. J. Simon, N. Eidelman, Y. Deng, N. R. Washburn, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 2003; b) C. G. J. Simon, N. Eidelman, S. B. Kennedy, A. Sehgal, C. A. Khatri, N. R. Washburn, *Biomaterials* **2005**, *26*, 6906; c) P. Xue, W. Liu, Z. Gu, X. Chen, J. Nan, J. Zhang, H. Sun, Z. Cui, B. Yang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11*, 1595.
- [81] B. M. Vogel, J. T. Cabral, N. Eidelman, B. Narasimhan, S. K. Mallapragada, *J. Comb. Chem.* **2005**, *7*, 921.
- [82] a) F. Blanc, S. Y. Chong, T. O. McDonald, D. J. Adams, S. Pawsey, M. A. Caporini, A. I. Cooper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 15290; b) J. Leisen, I. J. Gomez, J. A. Roper, J. C. Meredith, H. W. Beckham, *ACS Comb. Sci.* **2012**, *14*, 415.
- [83] a) S. T. Popovici, P. J. Schoenmakers, *J. Chromatogr. A* **2005**, *1099*, 92; b) H. Pasch, P. Kilz, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, *24*, 104; c) X. Villareal, H. Barth, *Am. Lab.* **2009**, *41*, 20.
- [84] a) G. Montaudo, F. Samperi, M. S. Montaudo, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2006**, *31*, 277; b) M. A. R. Meier, U. S. Schubert, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2005**, *76*, 062211.
- [85] A. J. Urquhart, D. G. Anderson, M. Taylor, M. R. Alexander, R. Langer, M. C. Davies, *Adv. Mater.* **2007**, *19*, 2486.
- [86] S. Wijnans, B.-J. de Gans, F. Wiesbrock, R. Hoogenboom, U. S. Schubert, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 1958.
- [87] A. L. Hook, J. Yang, X. Chen, C. J. Roberts, Y. Mei, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, M. R. Alexander, M. C. Davies, *Soft Matter* **2011**, *7*, 7194.
- [88] A. L. Hook, H. Thissen, N. H. Voelcker, *Langmuir* **2009**, *25*, 9173.
- [89] a) M. R. VanLandingham, J. S. Villarrubia, W. F. Guthrie, G. F. Meyers, *Macromol. Symp.* **2001**, *167*, 15; b) C. A. Tweedie, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, K. J. Van Vliet, *Adv. Mater.* **2005**, *17*, 2599.
- [90] a) J. Laeuger, M. Krenn, *Annu. Techn. Conf. – Soc. Plast. Eng.* **2008**, *66*, 1867; b) M. B. Kossuth, D. A. Hajduk, C. Freitag, J. Varni, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2004**, *25*, 243.
- [91] a) J.-L. Sormana, J. C. Meredith, *Mater. Res. Innovations* **2003**, *7*, 295; b) J.-L. Sormana, J. C. Meredith, *Macromolecules* **2004**, *37*, 2186; c) J.-L. Sormana, S. Chattopadhyay, J. C. Meredith, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **2005**, *76*, 062214.
- [92] K. A. Bunding Lee, S. C. Johnson, *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* **1993**, *28*, 231.
- [93] Q. Dong, H. Zang, A. Liu, G. Yang, C. Sun, L. Sui, P. Wang, L. Li, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* **2010**, *53*, 274.
- [94] J. B. Thorstenson, L. K. Petersen, B. Narasimhan, *J. Comb. Chem.* **2009**, *11*, 820.
- [95] P. Marizza, S. S. Keller, A. Müllertz, A. Boisen, *J. Controlled Release* **2014**, *173*, 1.
- [96] N. Eidelman, C. G. J. Simon, *J. Res. Natl. Inst. Stand. Technol.* **2004**, *109*, 219.

- [97] S. Baudis, A. Lendlein, M. Behl, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2014**, 299, 1292.
- [98] a) G. Steiner, E. Koch, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2009**, 394, 671; b) S. Liyanage, N. Abidi, *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* **2020**, 55, 840.
- [99] a) A. Tuchbreiter, J. Marquardt, J. Zimmermann, P. Walter, R. Mülhaupt, B. Kappler, D. Faller, T. Roths, J. Honerkamp, *J. Comb. Chem.* **2001**, 3, 598; b) L.-S. Wan, Z.-K. Xu, X.-J. Huang, Z.-G. Wang, J.-L. Wang, *Polymer* **2005**, 46, 7715.
- [100] a) R. A. Potyrailo, R. J. Wroczynski, J. E. Pickett, M. Rubinsztajn, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2003**, 24, 123; b) Y. Yang, D. Bolikal, M. L. Becker, J. Kohn, D. N. Zeiger, C. G. J. Simon, *Adv. Mater.* **2008**, 20, 2037.
- [101] H. Bakhshi, M. J. Zohuriaan-Mehr, H. Bouhendi, K. Kabiri, *Polym. Test.* **2009**, 28, 730.
- [102] a) A. E. Tonelli, J. L. White, in *Physical Properties of Polymers Handbook* (Ed: J. E. Mark), Springer, New York **2007**, Ch. 20, p. 359; b) T. Kitayama, K. Hatada, *NMR Spectroscopy of Polymers*, Springer, Berlin Heidelberg **2004**.
- [103] V. Sans, L. Porwol, V. Dragone, L. Cronin, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, 6, 1258.
- [104] a) S. Ren, R. Dawson, A. Laybourn, J.-x. Jiang, Y. Khimyak, D. J. Adams, A. I. Cooper, *Polym. Chem.* **2012**, 3, 928; b) S. Hug, M. E. Tauchert, S. Li, U. E. Pachmayr, B. V. Lotsch, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2012**, 22, 13956.
- [105] O. Ouari, T. Phan, F. Ziarelli, G. Casano, F. Aussenac, P. Thureau, D. Gimes, P. Tordo, S. Viel, *ACS Macro Lett.* **2013**, 2, 715.
- [106] D. Berek, *J. Sep. Sci.* **2010**, 33, 315.
- [107] S. Baudis, A. Lendlein, M. Behl, *Macromol. Symp.* **2014**, 345, 105.
- [108] J.-C. Zhao, *Chin. Sci. Bull.* **2014**, 59, 1652.
- [109] M. Behl, M. Balk, U. Mansfeld, A. Lendlein, *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2021**, 306, 2000672.
- [110] C. E. Blanchet, A. V. Zozulya, A. G. Kikhney, D. Franke, P. V. Konarev, W. Shang, R. Klaering, B. Robrahn, C. Hermes, F. Cipriani, D. I. Svergun, M. Roessle, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* **2012**, 45, 489.
- [111] K. Merrett, R. M. Cornelius, W. G. McClung, L. D. Unsworth, H. Sheardown, *J. Biomater. Sci., Polym. Ed.* **2002**, 13, 593.
- [112] a) A. Hansen, R. Zhang, M. Bradley, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2012**, 33, 1114; b) M. D. Kurkuri, C. Driever, G. Johnson, G. McFarland, H. Thissen, N. H. Voelcker, *Biomacromolecules* **2009**, 10, 1163; c) A. Michelmore, L. R. Clements, D. A. Steele, N. H. Voelcker, E. J. Szili, *J. Nanomater.* **2012**, 2012, 839053.
- [113] a) V. H. Pérez-Luna, T. A. Horbett, B. D. Ratner, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res.* **1994**, 28, 1111; b) J. Yang, Y. Mei, A. L. Hook, M. Taylor, A. J. Urquhart, S. R. Bogatyrev, R. Langer, D. G. Anderson, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Biomaterials* **2010**, 31, 8827.
- [114] D. G. Castner, B. D. Ratner, *Surf. Interface Anal.* **1990**, 15, 479.
- [115] D. Léonard, H. J. Mathieu, *Fresenius' J. Anal. Chem.* **1999**, 365, 3.
- [116] a) M. Taylor, A. J. Urquhart, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Surf. Interface Anal.* **2009**, 41, 127; b) A. J. Urquhart, M. Taylor, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Anal. Chem.* **2008**, 80, 135.
- [117] a) A. D. Celiz, A. L. Hook, D. J. Scurr, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Surf. Interface Anal.* **2012**, 45, 202; b) N. Scoutaris, A. L. Hook, P. Gellert, C. J. Roberts, M. R. Alexander, D. J. Scurr, *J. Mater. Sci.: Mater. Med.* **2012**, 23, 385; c) D. J. Scurr, A. L. Hook, J. Burley, P. M. Williams, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Surf. Interface Anal.* **2013**, 45, 466.
- [118] a) J. H. Lee, H. B. Lee, *J. Biomater. Sci., Polym. Ed.* **1993**, 4, 467; b) J. H. Lee, G. Khang, J. W. Lee, H. B. Lee, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **1998**, 205, 323; c) H. T. Spijker, R. Bos, W. van Oeveren, J. de Vries, H. J. Busscher, *Colloids Surf., B* **1999**, 15, 89; d) M. Zelzer, R. Majani, J. W. Bradley, F. R. A. J. Rose, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Biomaterials* **2008**, 29, 172; e) J. Yang, F. R. A. J. Rose, N. Gadegaard, M. R. Alexander, *Adv. Mater.* **2009**, 21, 300; f) A. I. Neto, C. A. Custodio, W. Song, J. F. Mano, *Soft Matter* **2011**, 7, 4147.
- [119] M. Taylor, A. J. Urquhart, M. Zelzer, M. C. Davies, M. R. Alexander, *Langmuir* **2007**, 23, 6875.
- [120] K. M. Jablonka, D. Ongari, S. M. Moosavi, B. Smit, *Chem. Rev.* **2020**, 120, 8066.
- [121] S. Langner, F. Häse, J. D. Perea, T. Stubhan, J. Hauch, L. M. Roch, T. Heumueller, A. Aspuru-Guzik, C. J. Brabec, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, 32, 1907801.

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